

Science-Matrix

Canadian Biotechnology

January 2005

Scan of Canadian Strengths in Biotechnology

Prepared for the
National Research Council Canada
Research Program Support Office

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Science-Metrix specializes in the measurement and evaluation of science, technology and innovation. Our data collection and assessment methods include bibliometrics, scientometrics, technometrics, surveys and interviews, environmental scans, monitoring and intelligence gathering. We perform program and policy evaluations, benchmarking and sector analyses, market studies and strategic planning. Science-Metrix has a robust knowledge of life and environmental sciences.

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Executive Summary

Demonstrating responsible world leadership on biotechnology has been one of the ten key themes of the Canadian Biotechnology Strategy (CBS) since its creation in 1998. This position was reinforced in 2004 with the launch of the Government of Canada's Blueprint for Biotechnology. The Blueprint emphasizes that "Canada's leadership, both domestically and internationally, requires that the new Stewardship Framework is supported by leading edge regulatory research, foresight, capacity-building in regulatory sciences, dialogue with Canadians, and international cooperation", and recommends various initiatives to achieve the desired international impact.

One of these initiatives recognizes that the knowledge harnessed from biotechnology advances has a powerful potential to address critical issues in developing countries, and recommends the establishment of a new national initiative for international development. This initiative would facilitate the coordination of strategic research and technology development networks encompassing research centers in Canada and developing countries.

As part of this initiative, the National Research Council of Canada (NRC) mandated Science-Metrix to undertake an environmental scan with the aim of identifying Canada's strengths in biotechnology in the public and private sectors, universities and hospitals. The scope of this scan includes science, research and technology developments, and innovation support activities (market intelligence, industrial technology advice, intellectual property management, commercialization support, etc.)

To assess science and technology (S&T) strengths beyond anecdotal evidence, Science-Metrix performed scientometric and technometric analyses. These techniques were used to identify in particular, biotechnology niches where Canada has a favourable position within the international community. The scientometric analysis involved surveying the Medline (US National Library of Medicine) and SCI Expanded (ISI Thomson) databases while the technometric analysis surveyed the USPTO (US Patent Office) database. In addition, a review of the literature was conducted to pinpoint significant individual scientific achievements in biotechnology. Identifying the strengths in the Canadian innovation system, involved reviewing the existing literature and information available on the internet on biotechnology developments in Canada.

Strengths in Biotechnology R&D in Canada

- Canada's greatest strengths in non-health biotechnology are in forestry, aquatic sciences, environmental and animal sciences, and in health biotechnology are in the area of diabetes, hormone research, stem cell research and the musculoskeletal system;
- Canada is the most specialized of the top-ten countries in forest biotechnology. Canada performs particularly well in the study of fungal diseases of trees, in population and quantitative genetic studies of trees, and genetic engineering of trees;
- In aquatic biotechnology, Canada ranks 2nd both for the expected impact of its scientific papers and its specialization in the field. The areas of major importance for Canada in this field are aquaculture, in particular enhancement of fish performance, molecular ecology to study wild populations, and biomonitoring of aquatic ecosystems;

- In environmental biotechnology, Canada ranks 1st for specialization, 2nd for volume of scientific output, and 3rd for the expected impact of its scientific papers. Canadian research in this area focuses on bioremediation of contaminated soil, water and air, or biotreatment of domestic, agricultural and industrial wastes using, for example, bioreactors for pollutant biodegradation;
- In animal science biotechnology, Canada far outranks other top-ten countries with respect to the expected impact of its scientific papers, and is the 3rd most specialized in the field. Canada's main scientific activities relate to bovines and consist of the production of vaccines against viral and bacterial diseases, and the development of efficient diagnostic tools for viruses, parasites and bacteria;
- Canada is the 2nd most specialized country in diabetes biotechnology and has a significant number of papers in the field. An important aspect of biotech research on diabetes in Canada pertains to the study of diverse hormones, such as insulin, glucagon and HISS, to treat diabetes patients;
- In musculoskeletal biotechnology, Canada is the most specialized amongst leading countries, and the expected impact of its scientific papers is good on average. The musculoskeletal disorders receiving most attention in Canada are arthritis, muscular dystrophies, multiple sclerosis, Huntington's disease and cardiac disorders;
- With respect to hormone biotechnology, Canada ranks 3rd for specialization and 2nd for the expected impact of its papers. In Canada, the focus of biotech research on hormones is undoubtedly therapeutics, similar to the focus on insulin and glucagon for the treatment of diabetes;
- Canada has a long history of excellence in stem cell research with 16 out of 35 classic stem cell papers published in the last half of the 20th century coming from Canada (*Nature Immunology*). Canadian scientists set the framework in which stem cells are currently being studied, and have made key discoveries on both adult and embryonic stem cells.

Strengths in the Canadian Biotechnology Innovation System

- In Canada, there is close connection between the government, academia and the private sector, which is referred to as the "triple-helix dynamics", and which creates an environment conducive to the establishment of start-ups that contribute to the expansion of technological clusters and to economic growth;
- The Government of Canada, through the NRC, catalyzed the emergence of a biotechnology cluster in Montreal, which created jobs and fuelled economic growth in the region. NRC was also the catalyst for the growth of the biotechnology cluster located in Saskatoon;
- In Canada, NRC plays a crucial role as an incubator for new biotech companies. NRC nurtures young firms, allowing them to survive and grow during the start-up period when they are most vulnerable. Through co-location, NRC provides companies with direct access to its facilities, services, and expensive equipment and the expertise of its researchers. In addition, NRC offers office space for low rents;
- Canada has numerous programs supporting the biotechnology scientific base. For instance, Genome Canada, with a budget of CDN\$375 million, established five genome centers across the country with the goal of making Canada a world leader in genomics and proteomics in areas such as agriculture, the environment, fisheries, forestry and health. Another important contributor is the Canada Foundation for Innovation (CFI), which aims to strengthen Canada's research capability by renewing its scientific infrastructure. In 1989, the Canadian government introduced the Networks of Centers of Excellence (NCE) program to enhance the links between academic and industry researchers. There are now NCEs pertaining to biotechnology and these reinforce the triple-helix dynamics. Finally, two federal programs provide funding for research that touches upon biotechnology, namely the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada (NSERC) and the Canadian Institutes of Health Research (CIHR);

- Canadian biotechnology companies benefit from several public and private sources of support for commercialization. The NRC's Industrial Research Assistance Program (IRAP) offers financial assistance for early stage R&D to help SMEs grow. The Trade Team Bio-Industries' (TTC BIO) international business strategy promotes Canadian biotech capabilities in the international marketplace, gathers, and disseminates to Canadian industry, foreign market intelligence, and supports initiatives that promote a domestic business climate conducive to the growth of an internationally competitive bio-industry. Industry Canada has created an investment loan fund, the Technology Partnerships Canada (TPC), to provide support for the development and export of high-tech products. Biotech companies also receive support for exporting their products from Export Development Canada (EDC), New Exporters to Overseas program (NEXOS), and the Canadian Commercial Corporation (CCC). Additionally, the International Business Opportunities Centre (IBOC) matches up capable Canadian firms with business opportunities abroad;
- Canada has a relatively solid regulatory system for the protection of intellectual property, affording effective protection for companies or researchers that develop new technologies or new products. Canada has adopted a national strategy to align its regulatory systems with those of the US and the EU in order to remain competitive and continue to encourage industrial development;
- The availability of venture capital, which is well developed in Canada, is a key factor in the creation and development of firms in Canada's biotechnology cluster. In terms of the size of their respective populations, the availability of venture capital for biotechnology in Canada compares favourably with the situation in the US;
- Canada has a competitive business environment with a tax regime that is highly conducive to expenditure on R&D. Canada's capital tax is being reduced in stages over a period of five years and will be eliminated by 2008, which will make it the most favourable country of the G7.

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1 Introduction

The launch of the Government of Canada's Blueprint for Biotechnology in 2004, emphasized that "Canada's leadership, both domestically and internationally, requires that the new Stewardship Framework is supported by leading edge regulatory research, foresight, capacity-building in regulatory sciences, dialogue with Canadians, and international cooperation", and recommends various initiatives to achieve the desired international impact. One of these initiatives recognizes that the knowledge being harnessed from biotechnology advances has a powerful potential to address critical issues in developing countries, and recommends the establishment of a new national initiative for international development. The Federal Biotechnology Deputy Minister's Coordinating Committee (BDMCC) has approved funding for a background analysis of the key areas where biotechnology programming would be of most strategic use in creating benefits to tackle development objectives and address risks.

As part of this study, the National Research Council of Canada (NRC) is leading a project that aims to scan Canadian strengths in innovation in biotechnology. Within this mandate, NRC selected Science-Metrix to perform an analysis with three objectives:

- To identify key players and strategic partners in biotechnology research and innovation within the public and private sectors across the Canada and summarize their relevant involvement;
- To identify and summarize niche strengths in biotechnology research and technology development in Canada;
- To identify and summarize strengths in the Canadian innovation system including such aspects as R&D capacity, research networks, funding mechanisms, industrial technology advice, intellectual property management, commercialization support, access to capital, market intelligence, etc.

The Canadian biotechnology industry

The biotechnology industry is based on the commercial exploitation of cellular or molecular research on animal, plant, or microbial species. This means that, unlike many other industries, biotechnology is defined not by its products, but by the technologies it uses (Bacon, 2003). Biotechnology is one of the world's fastest growing technologies. It has the potential to produce significant economic impacts, particularly in terms of exports and job creation, as well as important health, safety and environmental benefits.

Biotechnology is a Canadian success story: Canada has one of the largest biotechnology industries in the world (UK Trade & Investment, 2002; Datamonitor, 2004). Since the early stages of the industry, the Canadian government has actively supported the sector through sustained investments in laboratory and clinical research, as well as infrastructures.

The Canadian industry has grown steadily since 1997 from 282 companies to 496 in 2003 (Table I). The core activities of these companies involve the commercialization of bioscience research and development (R&D), and the development of bioscience-based products or services. Quebec has the

largest number of firms closely followed by Ontario. British Columbia is also an important player with close to a hundred companies in 2003.

Table I Biotechnology companies by province

Province	1997	1999	2001	2003
Quebec	79	107	130	146
Ontario	87	111	101	130
British Columbia	52	71	69	93
Alberta	19	28	24	44
Saskatchewan	19	16	17	35
Atlantic	20	19	23	27
Manitoba	6	6	11	21
Total	282	358	375	496

Source: Compiled by Science-Metrix from Statistics Canada's Biotechnology Use and Development Surveys

The biotechnology industry is an important employer. Since 2001 about 12,000 people have been involved in biotechnology-related activities (Table II). Quebec has the highest employment, although employment in biotechnology declined significantly in this province between 2001 and 2003, while in other locations, with the exception of the Atlantic, it has grown steadily.

Table II Biotechnology employment by province

Province	1997	1999	2001	2003
Quebec	2722	2557	4710	3695
Ontario	3416	2547	3346	3557
British Columbia	1042	1191	1746	2158
Manitoba	209	357	936	1213
Alberta	789	574	494	718
Saskatchewan	351	289	262	380
Atlantic	490	181	402	210
Total	9019	7696	11896	11931

Source: Compiled by Science-Metrix from Statistics Canada's Biotechnology Use and Development Surveys

The Canadian biotechnology market reached US\$4.4 billion in 2003, with a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of about 40% in the 1999-2003 period. This growth was significantly stronger than that of the global international market, leading to an increase of 2.8% in the Canadian share of the global market between 1999 and 2003. Currently the Canadian market accounts for about 5% of the global market. With increasing investment from the Canadian government and Canadian and US venture capitalists, the Canadian biotechnology market looks set for sustained growth albeit at a slower rate than during the 1999-2003 period.

According to Statistics Canada, the revenues of firms dedicated to biotechnology research were close to \$4 billion in 2003. While, in aggregate, Quebec's firms had the highest revenues in 2001, these subsequently plummeted and Ontario and British Columbia overtook Quebec in terms of biotechnology-related revenues in 2003 (Table III). The most important source of revenue for the Canadian biotechnology industry in 2003 was product sales, which accounted for 60% of the market's value. Over the next five years, the market is expected to experience slightly weaker growth rates as the market matures.

Table III Biotechnology revenues by province (CDN\$ million)

Province	1997	1999	2001	2003
Ontario	363	635	1376	2026
British Columbia	47	138	414	780
Quebec	224	554	1515	480
Alberta	56	90	122	298
Manitoba	33	69	99	145
Saskatchewan	56	433	21	71
Atlantic	34	28	22	21
Total	813	1947	3569	3821

Source: Compiled by Science-Metrix from Statistics Canada's Biotechnology Use and Development Surveys

In 2003, 18 of the recorded Canadian biotech firms were working in bioinformatics. Revenues for these 18 firms went from \$20 million in 1999 to an estimated \$144 million in 2002. Canadian bioinformatics exports were \$33 million in 2002, much of which went to the US (Canadian Trade Commissioner Service, 2002). By 2008, the market is expected to reach US\$8.7 billion, equating to a CAGR of 15% in the 2003-2008 period, slightly higher than the predicted global CAGR of 13% (Datamonitor, 2004).

Table IV shows that the most important sector in the biotechnology industry is health, which includes therapeutic and diagnostic applications. The food-centered sector is also significant, mainly comprising agriculture and food processing while aquaculture plays only a marginal role in terms of both revenue and the number of companies involved. Environment generates 7.5% of revenues and comprises about 9% of the companies, while bioinformatics and natural resources are marginal in terms of both revenues and number of firms. New areas of research in the Canadian biotechnology industry include stem cell research, nanotechnology, bioterrorism and drug discovery (Canadian Trade Commissioner Service, 2002).

- **Stem Cell Research:** After much debate and controversy, federal funds are now available for research using human embryonic stem cell lines approved by the Government;
- **Nanotechnology:** The current applications of nanotechnology for the biotechnology industry lie chiefly in the fields of diagnostics and therapeutics;
- **Bioterrorism:** Continued concerns about bioterrorism have focused interest not only on the development of vaccines, antibodies and biomedical therapies, but also on biosensors as a tool for the detection of bioterrorism threats;

- **Mapping vs. Drug Discovery:** Investment is moving away from gene and protein mapping towards drug development and marketing.

Table IV Biotechnology firms and revenues by sector

Sector	Revenues (\$ million)		Number of firms	
Human Health	2,461	69.0%	197	52.5%
Agriculture Biotechnology	245	6.9%	65	17.3%
Food Processing	581	16.3%	48	12.8%
Environment	268	7.5%	33	8.8%
Aquaculture	5	0.1%	11	2.9%
Bioinformatics	2	0.1%	11	2.9%
Natural Resources	7	0.2%	10	2.7%
Total	3,569	100%	375	100%

Source: Compiled by Science-Metrix from Statistics Canada's Biotechnology Use and Development Surveys

Canada's success in biotechnology is in part due to the early development of a national biotechnology strategy in 1983, and the country is determined to retain its leadership. This is being helped by the active support being given by several provincial governments for the development of biotechnology. For instance, as far back as 1982 the Quebec government introduced a policy (*À l'heure des biotechnologies*) for biotechnology research. Also in 1999 the Ontario government announced the creation of a \$20 million Biotechnology Commercialization Centre Fund as a part of its Superbuild Growth Fund to boost Ontario's competitiveness in biotechnology (KPMG, 1999). More recently, in 2003, Ontario announced the Biotechnology Cluster Innovation Program (BCIP) with the objective of making the province one of the top three biotech centres in North America. The aim of this \$30 million program is to support commercialization infrastructure projects such as research parks and other initiatives that promote entrepreneurship and innovation.

Canada has internationally renowned scientists, increasing numbers of leading-edge biotechnology companies and government policies with renewed emphasis on encouraging innovation and entrepreneurship.

2 Strengths in biotechnology R&D in Canada

This section draws a general picture of the trends in biotechnology science and technology over a 12-year period spanning 1992 to 2003 (Section 2.1 and 2.2) and subsequently identifies the most active institutions in biotechnology R&D (Section 2.3). This is followed by a review of significant accomplishments by Canadian scientists in biotechnology (Section 2.4) and an analysis in which specific fields have been delineated using precise keywords with the aim to identify biotechnology niches where Canada excels (Section 2.5).

In order to characterize the scientific and technological output of countries, a variety of bibliometric and technometric indicators was used in these sections:

- **Number of papers or patents;**
- **Specialization Index (SI):** this is an indicator of the intensity of research in a specific research area in a country relative to the intensity of research in the same research area in the world. A score above one means that a country specializes in the research area relative to the rest of the world;
- **Relative Average Impact Factor (RAIF):** this is an indicator of the average of expected impact of papers published by a country in a specific research area, relative to the average of expected impact of world's papers in the same research area. A score above one indicates that, on average, a country's papers have a higher expected impact than the average paper at the world level;
- **Relative Average Citations (RAC):** this is an indicator of the number of times a country's patents are cited on average in a specific research area relative to the world average in the same research area. A score above one indicates that, on average, a country's patents are cited more often than the average patent at the world level.

The bibliometric analysis involved a scan of both the Medline (US National Library of Medicine) and SCI Expanded (ISI Thomson) databases, while the technometric analysis was carried out using the United States Patents and Trademark Office (USPTO) database.

2.1 Biotechnology science in Canada

This section examines the growth of biotechnology papers in the SCI Expanded database at the Canadian level (Section 2.1.1) and ranks Canadian output at the international level (Section 2.1.2). Section 2.1.3 presents the distribution of papers by sector of activity.

2.1.1 Evolution of Canadian scientific output in biotechnology, 1992-2003

The number of Canadian papers published in biotechnology has increased from about 680 in 1992 to about 890 in 2003, i.e. an overall growth of around 30% (Figure 1). However, growth has been somewhat uneven with annual growth varying from about -8% to 15% for an average annual growth of 2.7%. Over the period examined, Canada's share of world biotechnology papers decreased from 5% to 4.5% due to a higher rate of growth of international papers. In fact, the number of scientific papers published in biotechnology at the world level increased from about 13,000 in 1992 to about 20,000 in 2003, i.e. an overall growth slightly above 50%. For the twelve-year period studied (1992-

2003), Canada ranks 6th for scientific output in biotechnology (9,619 papers), behind the US, Japan, the UK, Germany and France.

Figure 1 Scientific output in biotechnology for Canada, 1992-2003

Source: Compiled by Science-Matrix from SCI Expanded (Thomson ISI)

2.1.2 Ranking Canadian scientific output in biotechnology, 1999-2003

To obtain a snapshot of the current positioning of Canada within the international community, a ranking of leading countries was performed for the five years from 1999 to 2003 (Figure 2). In terms of number of scientific papers, Canada again ranks 6th (4,187 papers) in this period behind the US, Japan, Germany, the UK and France. With a specialization index (SI) of 1.24 in biotechnology, Canada can be considered as specializing in biotechnology. This means that the proportion of scientific papers published in biotechnology by Canada (the proportion is relative to all Canadian papers in the SCI Expanded) is 24% greater than the proportion of papers in biotechnology for the whole world.

Despite this relatively high level of specialization, Canada ranks 8th with respect to this indicator behind the Republic of Korea, Japan, Switzerland, the Netherlands, Sweden, Germany and France. In terms of relative average impact factor (RAIF), Canada's papers have, on average, about 10% more expected impact than the average world paper and ranking 6th behind the US, Switzerland, the Netherlands, the UK and Sweden. Overall, Canada is on a par with France in 6th place based on a multicriteria ranking that takes into account the number of papers, the SI and the RAIF.

Figure 2 Positioning of Canada among leading countries for its scientific output in biotechnology, 1999-2003

Source: Compiled by Science-Metrix from SCI Expanded (Thomson ISI)

2.1.3 Distribution of biotechnology papers by sector of activity, 1992-2003

Worldwide, the main sectors of scientific activity in biotechnology are biomedical research (48%), clinical medicine (35%) and biology (8%) (Figure 3). Chemistry, earth & space, engineering & technology, physics, and mathematics account for the residual 9% of scientific activity in biotechnology. For Canada, the picture is similar with biomedical research, clinical medicine and biology accounting for 50%, 30% and 10% respectively of scientific activity in biotechnology.

Canada has a greater output in mathematics (0.1% of papers; 10 papers), earth & space (4% of papers; 385 papers), engineering & technology (1.8% of papers; 168 papers) and biology (10% of papers; 957 papers) relative to the world. Canada can be considered as specialized in these research areas based on SI scores of 3.04, 1.65, 1.36 and 1.17 respectively. Given the overall small number of papers

published in mathematics, the SI for this area might not be significant and should therefore be interpreted with caution. Canada is also specialized in the area of biomedical research where it has published close to 5,000 papers over the 12-year period. However, the proportion of biotechnology papers for Canada is only slightly greater than for the world on average for biomedical research (SI of 1.04).

Figure 3 Distribution of biotechnology papers by sector of activity for the world and Canada, 1992-2003

Source: Compiled by Science-Metrix from SCI Expanded (Thomson ISI)

2.2 Biotechnology patents owned by Canada

This section examines the growth of biotechnology patents granted to Canada by the USPTO (Section 2.2.1) and ranks Canadian output at the international level (Section 2.2.2). Section 2.2.3 presents the distribution of patents by type of application.

2.2.1 Evolution of Canadian patent output in biotechnology, 1992-2003

Between 1992 and 2003, the number of biotechnology patents granted by the USPTO at the Canadian level grew almost fivefold, that is, from about 60 to 280 (Figure 4). However, in 2001 the number of patents granted started decreasing: 280 in 2003 compared to about 330 in 2000, this latter being the highest level achieved during the period. This slowdown in biotechnology patenting

is also observable at world level, and the cautious stance of the US and UK governments towards patents involving the genome has been suggested as a possible explanation (Archambault, Campbell and Côté, 2004). For instance, as the Blair and Clinton administrations were actively discussing this matter in 1999, it is highly likely that patent examiners in the USPTO decided to adopt a prudent stance and did not grant patents whose legitimacy might be later contested. Another possible reason for the smaller number of patents granted in 2001 might be the technical problems plaguing the USPTO, that is, the substantial number of applications in the late 1990s for patents on expressed sequence tags (Archambault, Campbell and Côté, 2004). During the 12-year period (1992-2003), Canada's share of world biotechnology inventions increased from about 2% to 4%. With a total of 2,459 biotechnology inventions, Canada ranked 5th for the whole period behind the US, Japan, Germany and the UK.

Figure 4 Technological output in biotechnology for Canada, 1992-2003

Source: Compiled by Science-Metrix from USPTO data

2.2.2 Ranking Canadian technological output in biotechnology, 1999-2003

Here again, the goal was to obtain a picture of the current positioning of Canada within the international community. Therefore, the analysis of patent data was restricted to the last five years of the period only, that is, from 1999 to 2003 (Figure 5). In terms of number of inventions, Canada ranks 5th (1,571 inventions) in this period behind the US, Japan, Germany and the UK. With respect to patents, the US undoubtedly leads the way with close to 70% of all biotechnology inventions protected in their country. This supremacy of the US results in very low values of SI for all the remaining countries. Therefore, in order to establish whether or not Canada is specialized relative to countries other than the US, this country was omitted for the remainder of the analysis. In this case Canada is shown to be more than twice as specialized as the world in biotechnology with a specialization index (SI) of 2.17 and a ranking of 6th behind Denmark, Australia, Belgium, Israel and

the UK. In terms of relative average citations (RAC), Canada’s patents are, on average, cited about 25% more often than the average world patent: Canada ranks 3rd behind Switzerland and the Netherlands. Overall, based on a multicriteria ranking (which does not include the US) that takes into account the number of patents, the SI and the RAC, Canada is on a par with Denmark in 1st place.

Figure 5 Positioning of Canada among leading countries (excluding the US) for its technological output in biotechnology, 1999-2003

Source: Compiled by Science-Matrix from USPTO data

2.2.3 Distribution of biotechnology inventions by sector of activity, 1992-2003

In terms of technology, the field of biotechnology can be divided in 10 application sectors (human health; agriculture & aquaculture; environment; food processing; bioinformatics; natural resources; processes; testing & measurement; apparatus, article, component or material; composition, compound, cell or molecule). At the world level, the main sectors are human health (36%), testing & measurement (19%), processes (19%) and composition, compound, cell or molecule (10%) (Figure 6). In Canada, the picture is similar with human health; testing & measurement; processes; and composition, compound cell or molecule. These are accounting respectively for 44%, 17%, 13% and 8% of technological activity in biotechnology. Canada is specialized in the environmental sector where it has 43% more inventions (SI of 1.43; 121 inventions) than the world average. The country is also specialized in human health (SI of 1.23; 1,086 inventions) and in agriculture & aquaculture (SI of 1.15; 168 inventions).

Figure 6 Distribution of biotechnology inventions by sector of activity and enabling technology for the world and Canada, 1992-2003

Source: Compiled by Science-Metrix from USPTO data

2.3 Most active Canadian institutions in biotechnology R&D

This section shows that, not surprisingly, the most active institutions in terms of scientific production in biotechnology are generally the universities. Of those institutions that published more than 100 papers with biotechnology-related terms in their titles, only two are government organizations – Agriculture and Agri-food Canada and the National Research Council Canada, and two are hospitals – Mount Sinai Hospital of Toronto and the Hospital for Sick Children of Toronto.

2.3.1 Universities

Table V shows that the most active universities are Toronto, McGill, British Columbia, Alberta and Guelph.

Ontario has a strong presence with Toronto, Guelph, Western Ontario and McMaster. In addition to McGill, Quebec's other leading institutions are Université de Montréal and Université Laval. The Prairies are also present, with both U. of Saskatchewan and U. of Calgary with more than 150 papers each. The Maritimes have no institutions among the leaders.

2.3.2 Health sector institutions

Table VI shows that research on biotechnology in the health sector is clearly dominated by institutions in Ontario and Quebec.

The three leading institutions are all located in Toronto (Mount Sinai Hospital; Hospital for Sick Children; University Health Network) while the next ranked institutions are all from the province of Quebec (Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Québec, Institut de Recherche Clinique de Montréal, and McGill University Health Centre).

Table V Universities that publish the most in biotechnology

University	Papers
University of Toronto	533
McGill University	372
University of British Columbia	308
University of Alberta	244
University of Guelph	223
Université de Montréal	209
Université Laval	205
University of Calgary	189
University of Western Ontario	181
University of Saskatchewan	170
McMaster University	166

Source: Science-Metrix (Thomson-ISI: SCI Exp.)

Table VI Hospitals that publish the most in biotechnology

Hospital	Papers
Mount Sinai Hospital of Toronto	109
The Hospital for Sick Children	108
University Health Network	96
Centre hospitalier universitaire de Québec	72
Institut de recherche clinique de Montréal	36
McGill University Health Centre	36
Cancer Care Ontario	35
London Health Sciences Centre	35
Ottawa Hospital	29
Sunnybrook Womens Col. Health Sciences	26
Centre hosp. de l'Université de Montréal	25

Source: Science-Metrix (Thomson-ISI: SCI Exp.)

2.3.3 Governments

Table VII shows that Agriculture and Agri-food Canada and the National Research Council Canada are the government organizations that are by far the most active in the field of biotechnology.

Other organizations that published more than 5 papers per year on average are Environment Canada, Fisheries and Oceans Canada, Health Canada and Natural Resources Canada.

2.3.4 Companies

Table VIII shows which firms located in Canada publish the greatest number of papers in biotechnology. As might be expected, the number of papers published by private firms is relatively small, the most active company, Merck & Co., publishing about 30 times fewer papers than the most active university. Aventis is the second most active company in terms of biotechnology publications.

Because the commercial interests of companies push them to protect their assets rather putting them into the public domain as universities do, it is often more revealing to examine patents to determine which are the most active institutions.

Table IX shows that Aventis is the company located in Canada that is the most active in biotechnology research. Visible Genetics, Allelix, and Merck Frosst although all active show a combined number of patents that is still lower than that of Aventis.

Table VII Government organizations that publish in biotechnology

Department/organization	Papers
Agriculture and Agri-food Canada	191
National Research Council Canada	160
Environment Canada	71
Fisheries and Oceans Canada	59
Health Canada	41
Natural Resources Canada	41

Source: Science-Metrix (Thomson-ISI: SCI Exp.)

Table VIII Companies that publish the most in biotechnology

Company	Papers
Merck Frosst Canada	14
Aventis	13
Aqua Bounty Technologies	7
Biomira	7
Nexia Biotechnologies	7
MDS Inc.	6
Stemcell Technologies	6

Source: Science-Metrix (Thomson-ISI: SCI Exp.)

Table IX Companies that patent the most in biotechnology

Company	Patents
Aventis	122
Visible Genetics (now Bayer)	29
NPS Allelix	28
Merck Frosst Canada	22
Generex Biotechnology	14
Adherex Technologies	14
Syn X Pharma	12
ConjuChem	12
Boehringer Ingelheim	11
Amgen Canada	11
NeuroSpheres Holdings	10

Source: Science-Metrix (Thomson-ISI: SCI Exp.)

2.4 Significant accomplishments by Canadian scientists in biotechnology

In addition to the significant contributions to biotechnology that can be seen at the institutional level, Canadian scientists have made some noteworthy contributions. A team in Toronto directed by Dr. Scherer (Scherer *et al.*, 2003) sequenced the entire human chromosome 7 consisting in some 158 million DNA nucleotides and 1,917 genes. In addition, the study established 400 chromosome breakpoints associated with diseases, which is expected to have profound implications for our understanding of many diseases including cystic fibrosis, leukemia and autism.

The Michael Smith Genome Sciences Centre in British Columbia responded quickly to the SARS (Sudden Acute Respiratory Syndrome) epidemic, sequencing the coronavirus within 6 months of the first case being reported in China in November 2003 (Marra *et al.*, 2003). Researchers at Vancouver's SARS Accelerated Vaccine Initiative (SAVI) developed four prospective vaccines for SARS with two of them demonstrating potential in animal models 18 months after initiation of the project near the end of the sequencing initiative (Finlay *et al.*, 2004). The efforts of these researchers in Vancouver show that Canada has the scientific capacity to respond rapidly to threats from viruses.

A team from Agriculture and Agri-food Canada is developing a method to eradicate the spread of genes from transgenic crops to wild populations using a sterility gene that prevents seeds of genetically modified organisms (GMOs) from crossbreeding (Ripley and Beversdorf, 2003).

A team led by Viaznikova from the University of Ottawa's Heart Institute has developed a method to extract DNA from a single fingerprint in 15 minutes. In addition to reducing the time of extraction, the new technology is less expensive and provides enough starting material to perform genetic analysis for individual assignment in forensics. The new technology is under patent (2003).

Dr. Syed (Kaul *et al.*, 2004) from the University of Calgary made the discovery that nerve cells grown on a silicon microchip can learn and memorize information that can be communicated to the brain. Future work will be conducted on creating an interface between the chips and the human brain to develop a two-way communication system. Eventually this technology could be used to control artificial limbs, restore sight to the visually impaired, and revive memory function leading to possible treatments for Alzheimer's patients.

2.5 Niche strengths in biotechnology research

In order to identify niches in which Canada has potential strengths in biotechnology, it was necessary to delineate a subset of biotechnology papers. Because biotechnologies are applied across a wide array of domains, two subsets of papers were constructed using the Medline and SCI Expanded databases. The Medline database is well suited to the production of statistics on biomedical and clinical medicine research, while the SCI Expanded provides the widest coverage of high-quality scientific research across more than 150 specialities. SCI Expanded indexes approximately 5,900 of the world's leading scholarly scientific and technical journals. These journals are considered to be the most important peer-reviewed journals in their respective fields. They reflect significant scientific achievements and are the most widely cited journals in the world (over 80% of the world's citations).

The biotechnology subsets of papers from Medline and SCI Expanded were defined using the following definition of biotechnology:

The application of scientific and engineering principles to the processing of organic and inorganic materials by biological agents (biological organisms or biological substances) to provide goods and services.

Operationally, the construction of these datasets was based on Boolean queries that use keyword-in-title (Medline and SCI Expanded) and keyword-in-abstract (Medline). The keywords were selected as follows. First, papers were randomly selected from journals specialized in biotechnology; relevant keywords and keyword combinations were then singled-out from the titles of these papers in order to retrieve other papers in the field of biotechnology. Finally, the biotechnology keyword set was validated using the SCI Expanded database with the objective of selecting papers specific to the domain of biotechnology.

Subsequently, a word frequency analysis was carried out to identify niche-specific keywords that were more frequent in Canadian papers relative to world papers. In Medline, word indexing was performed on both the titles and abstracts, together with MeSH terms (MeSH terms are the US National Library of Medicine's controlled vocabulary thesaurus, composed of a "descriptor" and a "qualifier" which pinpoints a specific aspect of the concept represented by the descriptor). MeSH terms constitute a powerful tool for delineating precise scientific or technological domains. In the SCI Expanded, word indexing was performed on titles only. Once the occurrence of niche-specific keywords was obtained, those with the highest Canada-to-world ratio were retained as niches in which Canada potentially excels. For each niche, a new set of keywords was built to retrieve all relevant papers. Health biotechnology niches were investigated using Medline, while non-health biotechnology niches were investigated using the SCI Expanded. When using Medline, Canada was compared with the following countries: the US, Japan, the UK, Germany, France, Italy, Switzerland, Denmark, the Netherlands and Norway. When using the SCI Expanded, the top ten countries in terms of production of scientific papers were compared.

Since the goal was to identify current Canadian strengths in biotechnology, data for the last five years (1998-2003) only were included in the analysis. For a niche to be considered, publication of at least ten papers per year for the five year period in that niche was required. Figure 7 summarizes the results obtained for the 20 niches thus obtained. Indicators (SI, RAIF) are log transformed such that the origin (0, 0) represents the world level. For both indicators, a value above 0 means that the score is higher than the world level, while a value below 0 means that the score is inferior to the world level. Consequently, strengths are to be found in the top right quadrant (high level of specialization, high level of expected impact). Conversely, the weakest niches are to be found in the lower left-hand quadrant.

In the top right quadrant of Figure 7, four non-health biotechnology niches clearly stand out as the most likely Canadian strengths in biotechnology. In decreasing order of angular distance from the world average coordinate (0, 0), these are forestry with 108 papers, aquatic sciences with 171 papers, environment with 389 papers and animal sciences with 180 papers. There are 9 other niches in the top right quadrant that are potential strengths. However, they are closer to the world level. Of these,

diabetes (137 papers), musculoskeletal system (477 papers), hormones (466 papers) and stem cell technology (279 papers), which are all health related, were retained as likely strengths in biotechnology because Canada publishes over 30 papers per year in these niches and it has good expected impact and specialization measured by the angular distance from the world average coordinate (0, 0). Sections 2.5.1 and 2.5.2 examine the positioning of Canada within the international community in terms of the most likely strengths in non-health and health biotechnology.

Legend		
ASC = Animal Sciences	DIA = Diabete	MSS = Musculoskeletal System
AQU = Aquatic sciences	DRD = Drug Delivery	PND = Psychologic & Neurologic Disorders
BOP = Bioprocesses	DRR = Drug Resistance	RSS = Respiratory Diseases
BCA = Breast Cancer	ENV = Environment	STD = Sexually Transmitted Diseases
CAN = Cancer	FOR = Forestry	STC = Stem Cell Technology
CVS = Cardiovascular System	HOR = Hormones	CHN = Congenital, Hereditary, and Neonatal Diseases and Abnormalities
VAC = Vaccines	IST = Insect Cell Technology	

Figure 7 Identification of biotechnology niches in which Canada excels, 1999-2003.

Source: Compiled by Science-Metrix from Medline and SCI Expanded (Thomson ISI)

2.5.1 Non-health Biotechnology

This section compares Canada relative to the leading countries in each of the following niches: forestry, aquatic sciences, environment and animal sciences. The data in this section are based on the SCI Expanded database.

Forestry

Growing demand for forestry products is not always compatible with the ecological role of the forest. Biotechnology is perceived as being an important potential way to conciliate human needs and other environmental needs. Tree agriculture might be the solution to the problem of producing sufficient forestry products on small surfaces with limited damage to the natural environment, but would be reliant on genetic improvements to the natural species and on intelligent pest management. Biotechnology is also used on such aspects as tree population monitoring, post harvest rehabilitation, and pulping operations.

Figure 8 presents the leading countries in forest biotechnology. With 215 papers published in this field, the US ranks 1st, followed by Japan and Canada with 124 and 108 papers respectively. With a similar number of scientific publications (100 papers), France ranks 4th. Germany and the UK, which rank 5th and 6th, published 92 and 67 papers respectively. Spain (53 papers), India (51 papers), China (42 papers) and Australia (38 papers) rank lowest among the leaders in terms of number of publications. In terms of the expected impact of papers, the US and the UK are equal leaders, with a RAIF of 1.31. They are followed by Australia (RAIF of 1.26) in 3rd place, France (RAIF of 1.22) in 4th place while Japan (RAIF of 1.14) ranks 5th. The expected impacts of Canada (RAIF of 1.06) and Germany (RAIF of 1.01) are near the world level, while Spain, China and India all have RAIF below the world level (0.92, 0.72 and 0.67 respectively). India is the most specialized country in this field with a SI of 2.51. Canada also has a high specialization (SI of 2.24) and is followed by Spain (SI of 1.69), France (SI of 1.48) and Australia (SI of 1.28). China (SI of 1.04) is slightly specialized, while Japan with SI of 0.95 is not specialized. The weakest countries in term of specialization are Germany (SI of 0.91), the UK (SI of 0.71) and the US (SI of 0.59).

Canada has an impressive specialization, ranking above most of the other countries with the exception of India. However, India's papers have the poorest expected impact and the country has published half as many papers as Canada. Thus, in terms of SI, Canada is an important leader in forest biotechnology. Looking at the number of papers and RAIF, France also appears to be leading in this area. Although Australia has a low volume of publications, this country is highly specialized and its papers have excellent expected impact. Therefore, Australia could be considered an important player in the field. Japan and Germany demonstrate average performance overall, although Japan has published a significant number of papers with good expected impact. Among the top ten countries in forest biotechnology, China is the weakest with small scientific output, low expected impact and marginal specialization.

Overall, Canada performs very well in forest biotechnology with good scientific output (it holds 3rd place in terms of number of publications and its papers have an acceptable expected impact) and impressive specialization compared to other countries in the top ten. Moreover, if one looks at other Canadian strengths, such as environment, diabetes, animal sciences, aquatic sciences and so on, the specialization of Canada in forest biotechnology clearly stands out (Figure 7). Thus, forest biotechnology represents a considerable strength for Canada. Within the niche of forest biotechnology, Canada performs very well in the study of fungal diseases of trees, population and

quantitative genetic studies of trees, and genetic engineering of trees. In fact, Canadian scientists from British Columbia, in collaboration with US researchers, were the first to genetically modify a gymnosperm species, white spruce, using DNA-coated micro-projectile bombardments (Ellis *et al.*, 1993). Canada also performs well in the study of insect pests, viral diseases of trees and viruses of tree pests. In addition, Canadian scientists are conducting research in the areas of bacterial diseases of trees, bacteria that attack tree pests, pulp and paper, symbiotic fungi, saprophytic fungi, and less common pathogens (nematode, plant).

Figure 8 Positioning of Canada among leading countries for its scientific output in forest biotechnology, 1999-2003

Source: Compiled by Science-Metrix from SCI Expanded (Thomson ISI)

In Canada, the field of forest biotechnology is led by three institutions: U. of British Columbia (UBC), NRCan and U. of Alberta (Table X) which published at least 5 papers per year on average. While there are many other players in the field, they do not publish nearly as many papers as the leading institutions.

Table X Canadian institutions that publish the most in forest biotechnology

Institution	Papers
University of British Columbia	29
Natural Resources Canada	27
University of Alberta	18

Source: Science-Metrix (Thomson-ISI: SCI Exp.)

Researchers from the University of British Columbia are mainly engaged in looking at fungal diseases of trees, insect pests and the development of transgenic trees. They are also conducting biotechnology research pertaining to the ecology of forest trees (e.g. population genomics and

response of trees to wounding, and to herbivores) and on the pulp and paper sector. At NRCan, a lot of work is being done on transgenic trees, fungal diseases of trees, insect pests, viruses and bacteria as biological control agents and ecology. At the University of Alberta, most biotechnology activities in forestry relate to the ecology of forest trees. For instance, researchers have been carrying out population genomics studies to establish the effect of harvesting and reforestation, and have been investigating the effect of herbivores and wounding on trees.

Aquatic sciences

Aquatic resources are often perceived as being crucial for fulfilling the growing need for food worldwide through aquaculture, which also has the potential to reduce the pressure on wild stocks. Biotechnology is at the core of aquaculture in permitting and optimizing the domestication of fish and shellfish species. It allows selection of favourable traits while limiting inbreeding. It also facilitates the development of innovative approaches to limiting pandemics. Also, the use of biotechnology tools to study the ecology (molecular ecology) of wild populations of aquatic organisms is essential to ensure the maintenance of wild stocks, and biodiversity, and to select adequate progenitors for aquaculture. Aquatic biotechnology is also suited for biomonitoring since many aquatic organisms are highly susceptible to contaminants.

The performances of the leading countries in the field of aquatic biotechnology are presented in Figure 9. For number of papers published, Canada ranks 4th with 171 of the 2,198 papers published in this area worldwide. Canada is outranked by the US (620 papers), Japan (356 papers) and the UK (232 papers). France and Germany hold 5th and 6th positions, with 162 papers and 137 papers respectively. The last four positions are held by Spain (103 papers), China (91 papers), Australia (81 papers) and Taiwan (68 papers). With respect to RAIF, the US is the clear leader (RAIF of 1.24) followed by Canada with a RAIF of 1.17, Germany with a RAIF of 1.11, and France and Taiwan which are almost on a par (RAIF of 1.07 and 1.06, respectively). Japan (IF of 0.95), the United Kingdom (IF of 1.02) and Spain (IF of 1.01) all exhibit expected impacts close to the world level. Finally, the lowest ranks are occupied by China and Australia, which both have RAIFs of 0.85. In terms of SI, Taiwan is clearly ahead with a SI of 2.8. Following quite far behind with a SI of 1.7, Canada holds the 2nd place. Spain, Japan and Australia are also quite specialized, having SIs of 1.58, 1.32 and 1.31 respectively. The UK (SI of 1.19), France (SI of 1.15) and China (SI of 1.09) are specialized and hold 6th, 7th and 8th place respectively. Both the US and Germany are not specialized in aquatic biotechnology, with SI of 0.82 and 0.65 respectively.

The US is probably the most important player in the field of aquatic science, publishing between a third and a quarter of all papers and obtaining the best expected impact. Taiwan is highly specialized in aquatic biotechnology, although its low number of publication is an indication that this result should be taken with caution. Japan and the UK are both important publishers and are also quite specialized in the area, although their impact is average. France combines good specialization, with good expected impact and a reasonable number of publications. Canada performs very well in aquatic biotechnology, ranking 2nd for both the RAIF and the SI. Canada is also quite far ahead of its nearest competitor in both cases, although at the same time it is a long way behind the first ranked

country. While the number of its publications is low, Canada still ranks 4th in that respect. Thus, aquatic sciences are clearly a solid strength in Canada’s biotechnology portfolio.

Figure 9 Positioning of Canada among leading countries for its scientific output in aquatic biotechnology, 1999-2003

Source: Compiled by Science-Matrix from SCI Expanded (Thomson ISI)

Aquaculture is the main sector of application of biotechnology to aquatic sciences. In Canada, aquaculture biotechnology mainly comprises development of genetically modified organisms (GMOs), mainly salmon (Coho salmon, Atlantic salmon), to enhance growth performance, disease resistance, and resistance to abiotic factors. Studies are also being conducted to develop vaccines, to improve phenotypic traits through artificial selection using conventional genetic approaches, to improve reproductive technologies, to develop a cleaner industry, and to develop diagnostic tools for fish diseases. Molecular ecology to study wild populations of aquatic organisms is also important in Canada. The majority of studies aim to provide a better understanding of population structure and dynamics using molecular markers. Among other things, these studies will help determine the status of natural populations, restore natural populations, establish the composition of fish stocks, and select progenitors for aquaculture. Another sector of importance to Canada in aquatic biotechnology is biomonitoring of aquatic ecosystems. Most biomonitoring studies involve either bivalves or fish as bioindicators.

The field of aquatic biotechnology is different from other Canadian niches in biotechnology in that there is a relatively strong presence of government departments (Table XI).

The leading institutions in this field comprise Fisheries and Oceans Canada, and Environment Canada (on a par with Guelph in 3rd place). Leading universities comprise Waterloo, Guelph, UBC and Laval.

Table XI Canadian institutions that publish in aquatic biotechnology

Institution	Papers
Fisheries and Oceans Canada	38
University of Waterloo	17
Environment Canada	15
University of Guelph	15
University of British Columbia	12
Université Laval	10

Source: Science-Metrix (Thomson-ISI: SCI Exp.)

The research activities of Fisheries and Oceans Canada are mainly directed to transgenic Coho salmon, molecular ecology to study fish stock composition, biomonitoring, bioremediation, and the development of vaccines for use in aquaculture. At the University of Waterloo, research in aquatic biotechnology primarily focuses on aquaculture with the goal of understanding the role of nutrition, hormones and growth factors to enhance fish growth and health. Ecotoxicology research on fish is also important. Not surprisingly, Environment Canada's scientific activities in this area consist of biomonitoring and bioremediation studies. Interestingly, Aquabounty Farms, a biotechnology firm devoted to aquaculture, ranks 3rd among the most active companies in biotechnology for scientific output (Table VIII). The company is mainly involved in the study of transgenic Atlantic salmon.

Environment

Biotechnology is surely one of keys to sustainable development. On the one hand, it facilitates development of more effective and less polluting processes for the production of goods, and on the other hand, it offers innovative means for detecting, monitoring and cleaning polluted air, soil and water. The niche identified here relates to this second aspect with an emphasis on biological treatment of domestic, agricultural and industrial wastes, and contaminated land and water.

Figure 10 presents the leading countries in environmental biotechnology. With 1,308 papers published in this area, the US leads in terms of number of publications, followed by Canada with 377 papers. Germany and Japan rank 4th and 5th with 357 and 355 papers respectively. The UK slightly misses the top five with 336 publications (6th). France occupies 7th place with 262 papers. Italy, the Republic of Korea and China have published similar numbers of papers, ranging from 201 to 215. Spain comes last among the top ten countries with 192 publications. In terms of RAIF, four countries score significantly higher than the world average. The UK (1st) and the US (2nd) have RAIFs of 1.27 and 1.24 respectively; Canada (RAIF of 1.13) and Spain (RAIF of 1.12) follow in 3rd and 4th place. Germany, Italy, France and Japan all have very similar expected impacts with RAIFs near the world level (ranging from 0.99 to 1.05). China and the Republic of Korea have the lowest expected impact (RAIF of 0.86 and 0.81 respectively).

Interestingly, Canada has a strong specialization in this field and ranks 1st. Canada's proportion of biotechnology papers in environment is 64% higher than the world proportion (SI of 1.64). The Republic of Korea and Spain rank 2nd and 3rd with SIs of 1.58 and 1.29 respectively. China and Italy

have only slightly more papers than the world average in environmental biotechnology in total biotechnology papers with a SI of 1.05. All the remaining countries have fewer papers than the world in environmental biotechnology proportionate to total biotechnology papers (France SI of 0.81; US and UK SI of 0.75; Germany SI of 0.74). Japan had the lowest level of specialization with a SI of 0.57.

Figure 10 Positioning of Canada among leading countries for its scientific output in environmental biotechnology, 1999-2003

Source: Compiled by Science-Metrix from SCI Expanded (Thomson ISI)

Although the UK has an excellent scientific output in terms of number of publications and expected impact, its level of specialization is low. Conversely, the Republic of Korea has a strong specialization, but it ranks last for the expected impact of its papers and it is among the least productive countries. China is one of the weakest countries among the top ten in environmental biotechnology with a relatively small number of publications, which have little expected impact; the country has only a marginal specialization in the field. Although Japan has published almost as many papers as Canada, it ranks lower in terms of expected impact and has the smallest SI. In general, Germany, France, and Italy display average performance for the field of environmental biotechnology. With a fairly high level of specialization and strong expected impact, Spain follows Canada among the leaders in this area.

Overall, Canada performs very well in environmental biotechnology. Since it is the world leader in terms of specialization, based on its scientific output (2nd place for number of publications) and the expected impact of its scientific publications (3rd place for RAIF), it is safe to assume that environmental biotechnology represents an important strength for Canada.

The main activity of Canadian researchers relates to the use of bioreactors for the biodegradation of pollutants towards either bioremediation of contaminated soil, water and air, or biotreatment of domestic, agricultural and industrial wastes. Biofiltration is also well established as a method for bioremediation and biotreatment. On site bioremediation often involves the use of bacteria inoculation. Parallel to bioremediation and biotreatment, ecotoxicology and biomonitoring are also important research activities in environmental biotechnology in Canada.

In Canada, Waterloo leads in scientific output in environmental biotechnology with 44 papers published between 1999 and 2003 (Table XII).

McGill, Toronto and UBC are also among the leaders while Guelph, Sherbrooke, the Université du Québec, and Université de Montréal make a substantial, but lesser contribution to the field.

Two government institutions are important: Environment Canada and the National Research Council Canada.

Table XII Canadian institutions that publish in environmental biotechnology

Institution	Papers
University of Waterloo	44
Environment Canada	38
National Research Council Canada	37
McGill University	32
University of Toronto	32
University of British Columbia	30
University of Guelph	22
Université de Sherbrooke	22
Université du Québec	21
Université de Montréal	21

Source: Science-Metrix (Thomson-ISI: SCI Exp.)

Among the top three institutions in environmental biotechnology, the University of Waterloo and the NRC put much emphasis on the study of biodegradation and bioremediation, while Environment Canada concentrates on ecotoxicology and biomonitoring. The University of Waterloo also conducts studies on biofiltration, biomonitoring and ecotoxicology. NRC also has an interest in biomonitoring and biofiltration. Finally, Environment Canada also conducts bioremediation, biomagnification and biofiltration studies. Recently, a team at the University of Saskatchewan led by Dr Krone, made an important breakthrough in the field of ecotoxicology and biomonitoring. The team created a transgenic fish carrying a green fluorescent protein gene. In the presence of toxins, stressed cells express the gene resulting in the fluorescence of affected body parts, sensory organs like the nose in zebrafish. Thus, the transgenic fish can be used to monitor or to assess the toxicology of diverse environmental toxins such as cadmium (Blechinger *et al.*, 2002).

Animal sciences

Science and technology for the production of genetically engineered animals has advanced very rapidly in the last few years. It is now possible to produce animals with novel properties for dairy, meat, or fibre production. Biotechnology can be used to directly transform animals, but can also be used for animal therapeutics, diagnosis and feed improvement.

Figure 11 presents the leading countries for animal science biotechnology. With 787 papers published in this area, the US is the leader in terms of publications, followed by Japan and Germany with 328 and 240 papers respectively. The UK (236) and Canada (180) which rank 4th and 5th have

produced similar numbers of publications. France comes 6th with 154 papers. Among the leaders, the lowest ranked countries in term of publications are Australia, India, Italy and Spain with numbers ranging from 81 to 115. For expected impact, Canada comes 1st with a RAIF of 1.30, followed by the US with a RAIF of 1.23. The papers from the UK and Spain have similar expected impacts with RAIF of 1.15 and 1.13 respectively. France (RAIF of 1.08) and Germany (RAIF of 1.06) come in 5th and 6th place. Australia's (RAIF of 1.0), Japan's (RAIF of 0.97) and Italy's (RAIF of 0.96) papers have an expected impact close to the world level. India is the weakest country in terms of expected impact with a RAIF of 0.32. For specialization, India (SI of 1.90), Australia (SI of 1.53) and Canada (SI of 1.47) are the countries with the highest levels of specialization in the field. Spain (SI of 1.02), Japan (SI of 1.00) and the UK (SI of 0.99) are only marginally specialized, while Germany, France, the US and Italy are not specialized with SI of 0.94, 0.90, 0.85 and 0.82 respectively.

Figure 11 Positioning of Canada among leading countries for its scientific output in animal science biotechnology, 1999-2003

Source: Compiled by Science-Metrix from SCI Expanded (Thomson ISI)

Despite their modest number, Canadian papers have a high expected impact on the scientific community. Furthermore, Canada is strongly specialized in this niche. Although Australia and India have a higher SI, they have relatively weaker scientific output in terms of number of publications and expected impact. Some countries, such as the US and the UK, have good scientific output, but do not specialize in the field. Other countries, like Japan, have published an impressive number of papers,

but they have a weak expected impact. In addition, they are only slightly specialized in the area. Thus, Canada surpasses all the other countries in terms of expected impact and specialization. Consequently, Canada can be considered to be a strong leader in animal science biotechnology. The field represents a considerable strength for Canada, possibly the most important among those identified.

Within animal science biotechnology, bovines received the greatest attention in Canada, with swine and fowls ranking next in importance. The main scientific activities in this area relate to the production of vaccines against viral and bacterial diseases, and to the development of efficient diagnostic tools for viruses, parasites and bacteria. The use of recombinant proteins, such as hormones, artificial selection and genetic transformation to increase production yields and quality is also important. Other research areas include the advance of reproductive technologies such as *in-vitro* fertilization and cloning, the cleaning of agricultural waste, and the development of breeding schemes.

Table XIII shows that the most active institutions in Canada in animal science biotechnology are Guelph, Saskatchewan and Agriculture and Agri-food Canada.

Universities from the province of Quebec are also very active since Montréal, Laval, the Université du Québec and McGill University are among the most active institutions in the field.

Table XIII Canadian institutions that publish in animal science biotechnology

Institution	Papers
University of Guelph	35
University of Saskatchewan	33
Agriculture and Agri-food Canada	32
Université de Montréal	24
Université Laval	12
Université du Québec	10
McGill University	10

Source: Science-Metrix (Thomson-ISI: SCI Exp.)

At the University of Guelph, the use of recombinant proteins, such as hormones, artificial selection and genetic transformation to increase production yield and quality predominates, although work on other aspects such as reproductive technologies and therapeutics is also ongoing. Research at the University of Saskatchewan mainly addresses issues related to therapeutics and diagnosis of diseases caused by viruses, parasites and bacteria. Vaccines development dominates. Agriculture and Agri-food Canada's research is diversified and addresses most of the areas mentioned above that are important to Canada. Recently, researchers from Caprion Pharmaceutical in Montreal in collaboration with a team from the University of Toronto found a molecular target on the protein associated with so called "mad cow" disease, or BSE. Their research is a major step forward towards finding a blood test to identify bovine spongiform encephalopathy (BSE) in cattle, thereby providing an alternative to mass slaughter, and eventually to producing a vaccine (Paramithiotis *et al.*, 2003).

2.5.2 Health biotechnology

This section benchmarks Canada relative to the leading countries in each of the following niche competences: diabetes, musculoskeletal system, hormones and stem cells. The data in this section are based on the Medline database.

Diabetes

Biotechnology and diabetes are strongly associated because the insulin needed by many diabetics has to be produced by living organisms or at least through biological means. In fact, the first approved biotechnology drug was recombinant human insulin produced in bacteria by Eli Lilly in 1982. Other approaches to treating diabetes encompass the reparation or the replacement of the natural insulin-producing tissues. Gene therapy can be used to deliver a gene that code for insulin or insulin-like hormone into the patient or for immunomodulation to prevent the onset of type I diabetes. Stem cell transplantation to replace islet cells in the pancreas is also a very effective way of treating type I diabetes.

Figure 12 presents important countries in diabetes biotechnology. With 994 papers published in this area, the US is the clear leader in terms of number of publications. It is followed by Japan with 270 papers. The UK ranks 3rd with 158 papers and is followed by Germany, Canada and France, which all have between 135 and 139 scientific papers. Italy comes in 7th place with 100 papers. Switzerland, Denmark and the Netherlands are among the weakest countries in terms of publications with 52, 39 and 31 papers respectively. In terms of expected impact, the US (1st rank), Denmark (2nd rank) and Switzerland (3rd rank) lead with RAIFs of 1.24, 1.13 and 1.12 respectively. France and the UK rank joint 4th with a RAIF of 1.07, followed by Canada and Italy which have expected impacts around the world level, with RAIFs of 1.05 and 0.94 respectively. Norway (RAIF of 0.85), the Netherlands (RAIF of 0.80), Germany (RAIF of 0.76) and Japan (RAIF of 0.75) all score below the world level with the lowest expected impact in all the countries analyzed. Denmark has the highest specialization with a SI of 1.72, followed by Canada with a SI of 1.49. Switzerland and Italy come in 3rd and 4th place with SIs of 1.26 and 1.16 respectively. The US (SI of 1.07) and France (SI of 1.02) are slightly specialized in the area, while the remaining countries are not specialized at all.

For number of papers and specialization, Canada, the US and Switzerland are among the leaders in diabetes biotechnology. Although Denmark and Italy have few publications with only small or average expected impact, these countries are highly specialized, particularly Denmark which ranks in 1st place in terms of SI. Overall, France and the UK display average performance. The Netherlands and Germany are the weakest countries in this field. Their scientific output has little expected impact and they are not specialized. Although Japan has published an impressive number of papers, they have fairly small expected impact and the country is not specialized.

Canada performs well in diabetes biotechnology. It is highly specialized (2nd place), has an important volume of publications and a RAIF about 5% above the world level (5th place). Diabetes biotechnology represents an important strength for Canada.

Figure 12 Positioning of Canada among leading countries for its scientific output in diabetes biotechnology, 1999-2003

Source: Compiled by Science-Metrix from Medline

The use of biotechnology to treat or monitor diabetes is a field that is relatively scattered in terms of scientific output by Canadian institutions (Table XIV). The universities of Calgary and of Toronto lead by a small margin and the University Health Network (Ontario) and the University of Manitoba are also among the leaders.

Table XIV Canadian institutions that publish in diabetes biotechnology

Institution	Papers
University of Calgary	17
University of Toronto	16
University Health Network	13
University of Manitoba	10

Source: Science-Metrix (Medline)

At the University of Calgary, emphasis is on fundamental research to understand the mechanisms behind autoimmune diabetes (type 1 diabetes). In 1999, scientists from Calgary published important results in *Science* demonstrating that autoimmune diabetes could be controlled by modulating the expression of the GAD gene in beta cells, thereby pointing to a potential new therapy (Yoon *et al.*, 1999). The University of Toronto has been at the heart of diabetes research since the discovery of insulin in 1921 by Banting, Best, Collip and Macleod. This discovery saved the lives of millions of people worldwide and in 1923 Banting and Macleod were awarded the Nobel Prize in physiology or medicine for their work. Nowadays, diabetes research in Toronto touches upon diverse aspects of the disease from causes to consequences, using biotechnology in order to develop new therapies. Recently, Seaberg *et al.* (2004) discovered cells in an adult pancreas capable of generating insulin-

producing beta cells. This finding could lead to an efficient treatment for diabetes in humans. The team is now working to determine whether or not these cells are stem cells. The study was supported by the Stem Cell Network and was published in *Nature Biotechnology*. Among other things, research at the University Health Network includes work to develop glucagon-like peptides for the treatment of diabetes, an area in which Canada appears to be well positioned.

Musculoskeletal system

Using the National Library of Medicine's definition of the musculoskeletal system, studies of the cardiac muscle are included in this section. Many disorders affect the musculoskeletal system and thus limit the mobility of people. Population aging is certainly increasing the occurrence of such problems and traditional biomedical and pharmaceutical approaches are often insufficient to develop solutions. Novel biotechnology tools are increasingly being used by researchers in their quest to treat these diseases. For example, many transgenic models have been developed to study rheumatoid problems and other major debilitating diseases such as muscular dystrophy. Furthermore, vast effort has gone into researching the replacement of damaged tissues through stem cell transplants and innovative biomaterials. Finally, new biopharmaceuticals are being developed to cure and prevent diseases such as osteoporosis using oestrogen-analogs, and arthritis using a panoply of recombinant antiarthritics.

From Figure 13, it can be seen that Canada is well positioned in the area of musculoskeletal biotechnology. Here again, the distribution of research production is skewed. The US (4,274 papers), Japan (1,271 papers) and Germany (790 papers) are shown to be the three most productive countries. Canada holds 6th position in terms of publication volume, with 477 papers. A number of countries are specialized in the field. Canada can claim the top position in this regard, with a SI of 1.28, followed by the Netherlands (SI of 1.15) and the US (SI of 1.14). Japan (SI of 1.08) and Italy (SI of 1.07) come next. The remaining countries are either slightly or not specialized with SI ranging from 0.91 to 1.02. Papers from the US have the highest expected impact, with a RAIF of 1.18, followed by Switzerland, with a RAIF of 1.16 and the UK, with a RAIF of 1.11. Canada comes in 4th position, with a RAIF of 1.07. The remaining countries have RAIFs varying between 0.81 for Germany to 1.02 for Denmark.

Canada displays good performance in musculoskeletal biotechnology. While its volume of publications is rather small compared to the other countries, it is the most specialized in the field and its papers have a good expected impact. Here again Canada is rather overshadowed by its neighbour the US, which offers all-around good performance.

Figure 13 Positioning of Canada among leading countries for its scientific output in musculoskeletal biotechnology, 1999-2003

Source: Compiled by Science-Metrix from Medline

Within Canada, the U. of Alberta and the U. of Toronto are the leading institutions for research on the use of biotechnology for musculoskeletal applications (Table XV).

In Alberta, the U. of Calgary is also active while Ontario counts the U. of Western Ontario, the U. Health Network and McMaster U. among the leading institutions in this field. Quebec and British Columbia have one leader each.

Table XV Canadian institutions that publish in musculoskeletal biotechnology

Institution	Papers
University of Alberta	36
University of Toronto	33
Centre hosp. de l'Université de Montréal	26
University of Western Ontario	25
University Health Network	24
University of British Columbia	23
McMaster University	22
University of Calgary	21

Source: Science-Metrix (Medline)

Within Canada, most research in musculoskeletal biotechnology relates to biomechanics and physiology of muscles and bones. Among musculoskeletal disorders, those receiving most attention are arthritis, muscular dystrophies, multiple sclerosis, Huntington's disease and cardiac disorders. At the University of Alberta and at the University of Toronto, the focus is on fundamental research to improve understanding of the mechanics and physiology of muscles and bones. The University of Toronto also does research on cardiac dysfunctions. The Centre Hospitalier de l'Université de Montréal (CHUM) clearly has expertise in using biotechnology to study arthritis (osteoarthritis and rheumatoid arthritis).

Recently, key advances were made by Dr. David of McGill University in understanding how the nervous system is attacked in multiple sclerosis patients. He and his co-workers found that by blocking the enzyme cPLA2, multiple sclerosis could be prevented in laboratory mice and could reduce symptoms in mice with the disease. cPLA2 is implicated in the destruction of myelin, an essential molecule for the transmission of impulses in the nerve cells of the brain and spinal cord (Kalyvas and David, 2004).

Another important breakthrough in the treatment of musculoskeletal diseases was made by researchers at the Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Québec (CHUQ). Quenneville *et al.* (2004) have developed a gene therapy to express dystrophin in the muscle cells of patients with Duchenne muscular dystrophy. Dystrophin, which is absent in patients with Duchenne's disease, is an essential protein preventing muscle fibers from breaking.

Hormones

Hormones are vital for the survival of multicellular organisms. Inability to produce hormones in their proper state and in sufficient quantity can lead to illness and death. Biotechnology offers a broad range of solutions to repair or replace damaged secreting tissues, or to replace missing hormones or cofactors. The first biotechnology-based hormonal therapeutic to be approved by the FDA (US Food and Drug Administration) was human insulin produced in bacteria in 1982; since then many recombinant hormones have been approved.

Results for the niche of hormone biotechnology are depicted in Figure 14. A striking aspect of this field is the uneven distribution of publications among countries. While the US has 4,115 papers in the field and Japan 1,122 papers, Norway only has 39 papers. Canada comes in 7th place for number of publications (466 papers), but ranks 3rd for specialization (SI of 1.20), behind Italy (SI of 1.36) and Denmark (SI of 1.24). The US follows with a SI of 1.05. Other countries are either slightly or not specialized in this niche application of biotechnology. Germany comes last with a SI of 0.80. Regarding the impact of scientific output, the US and Canada perform very well with scientific papers whose expected impact are 12% and 21% greater respectively than the world average papers expected impact. France is an important contender here, with good scores for all indicators (573 papers, RAIF of 1.04 and SI of 1.03).

Figure 14 Positioning of Canada among leading countries for its scientific output in hormones biotechnology, 1999-2003

Source: Compiled by Science-Metrix from Medline

Canada offers a limited but solid performance in the biotechnology niche of hormones. Its small number of publications is more than compensated for by its good specialization and the high expected impact of its papers. These factors explain why biotechnology applications in the area of hormones can be considered a major strength for Canada. Its performance is only overshadowed by that of the US, which publishes a huge number of publications, has the best expected impact, and a good SI.

Within Canada, biotechnology to produce and to perform research on hormones is clearly led by the U. of Toronto with 42 papers compared to 26 for the next most active institution (Table XVI).

There are 6 other Canadian institutions that published at least 4 papers per year on average in this field between 1999 and 2003.

Table XVI Canadian institutions that publish in hormones biotechnology

Institution	Papers
University of Toronto	42
University of Alberta	26
University Health Network	26
Centre hospitalier universitaire de Québec	25
University of Calgary	25
University of Manitoba	23
University of British Columbia	20

Source: Science-Metrix (Medline)

In Canada, hormones are studied and used in diverse contexts. The most widespread application of hormones is undoubtedly that of therapeutics (as is the case for insulin and glucagon in the treatment of diabetes). Also important is the use of hormones to enhance production yields, for example growth hormones in transgenic fish, and hormones (recombinant somatotropin) to increase milk protein production in dairy cows. The study of reproductive hormones is also important in Canada. Despite the benefits that can be gained from the use of hormones, these molecules are sometimes implicated in cancer and numerous papers on this have been published in Canada. At the University of Toronto, researchers are conducting studies on all these aspects with emphasis on hormones as therapeutics. In addition, they are looking at hormones as potential tools for insect pest control. At the University of Alberta and at the University Health Network, studies focus on hormones as therapeutics, reproductive hormones, and involvement of hormones in cancer. Recently, scientists from the University of Manitoba discovered a hormone that could heal type 2 diabetes. The hormone in question, HISS, is released in the liver after a meal, and is responsible for more than half of the storage of sugar in the muscles. Researchers found that people with type 2 diabetes have either no or low levels of HISS opening the way to an alternative or complement to insulin treatment (Lautt, 2004).

Stem cell technology

Stem cell research has been being conducted for approximately 40 years and brings the hope of finding treatments for a broad range of devastating diseases like diabetes, heart failure, spinal cord injuries, multiple sclerosis, Parkinson's and Alzheimer's diseases. There are two main types of stem cells: adult and embryonic stem cells. The former were discovered first, but they were rapidly overtaken by the latter because people thought their differentiation capacity was more limited. However, recent work on adult stem cells suggests that they have a broader differentiation capacity than first thought and might thus be a good alternative to embryonic stem cells since they raise fewer ethical issues. A large amount of ongoing research is directed to addressing technical problems associated with the proliferation of transplanted cells and immune rejection.

Figure 15 presents countries' performances regarding stem cell biotechnology. Canada fares rather poorly for volume of publications, in 7th position with 279 papers. It is dominated by the US (3,254 papers), Japan (1,039 papers) and Germany (750 papers), but also by countries such as Italy (397

papers). Although Canada has a SI of 1.13, usually a strong score, this only puts it in 9th position when compared to other countries. Italy holds the top ranking with a SI of 1.71. The Netherlands and Germany follow with SIs of 1.45 and 1.40 respectively. Denmark stands out as the only country not specialized in stem cell biotechnology with a SI of 0.72.

Figure 15 Positioning of Canada among leading countries for its scientific output in stem cell biotechnology, 1999-2003

Source: Compiled by Science-Metrix from Medline

It is in terms of expected impact that stem cell research stands out as a strength for Canada. The country ranks 2nd with a RAIF of 1.16, only slightly behind the US with a RAIF of 1.20. The Netherlands, the UK, Switzerland and France all have RAIFs around or slightly below the world average (between 0.89 and 1.01). Finally, the scientific outputs of Germany, Japan, Denmark and Italy have low expected impact, with RAIF ranging from 0.69 to 0.75. Although Canada ranked only 9th for the SI, the country’s proportion of biotechnology papers in stem cells is 13% higher than that for the world as a whole and it ranks 2nd with respect to RAIF. The expected impact of Canadian

papers is on average 16% higher than that of the average world paper. The leader is once again the US. The Netherlands is also a strong contender.

Table XVII presents the most active institutions in research involving biotechnology and stem cell research in Canada. The British Columbia Cancer Agency and the U. of Toronto are the leaders in the field and the U. Health Network is another important player.

Alberta also has an important player (U. of Calgary), while McGill U. is the only institution from Quebec with more than 3 papers annually in this field.

Table XVII Canadian institutions that publish in stem cell biotechnology

Institution	Papers
British Columbia Cancer Agency	35
University of Toronto	32
University Health Network	27
Toronto Public Health	20
University of Calgary	19
University of British Columbia	16
Hospital for Sick Children	15
McGill University	15

Source: Science-Metrix (Medline)

Canada has a long history of excellence in stem cell research. Till and McCulloch, two Canadians, were the pioneers of research on stem cells. In 1961, they demonstrated the existence of bone-marrow cells capable of self-renewal over time and differentiation into all cell types present in the blood, which led them to introduce the concept of stem cells. Their findings in the early 1970s, led to an efficient treatment for leukemias using bone-marrow transplants. Subsequently, Canadian scientists have been responsible for landmark discoveries in stem cell research. For example, Reynolds and Weiss (1992) from the University of Calgary were the first to isolate Neural Stem Cells (NSC), Nagy *et al.* (1993) from Mount Sinai Hospital were the first to definitely demonstrate the capacity of a single embryonic stem cell to regenerate a complete, normal, viable and fertile organism, the team of Dr. Van der Kooy from the University of Toronto was the first to isolate retinal stem cells from the adult mammalian eye (Tropepe *et al.*, 2000), and Dr. Miller's team from McGill University was the first to isolate adult stem cells from the dermis of mammalian skin capable of undergoing differentiation into neural cells (Toma *et al.*, 2001).

According to *Nature Immunology*, Canadian researchers have been involved in the most outstanding research into stem cell research, with 16 of 35 classic stem cell papers published in the last half of the 20th century being from Canada, nine of which are authored by Till and McCulloch who set the framework in which stem cells are studied today. In honour of the tremendous contribution of Till and McCulloch to the field of stem cell research, both researchers were inducted into the Canadian Medical Hall of Fame in 2004. The quality of all this research catalyzed the creation of a Canadian Network of Centres of Excellence in this area in 2000, the Stem Cell Network (Campbell, Noiseux and Côté, 2004).

3 Strengths in the Canadian biotechnology innovation system

Canada has tangible comparative advantages in terms of its national system of innovation, in biotechnology. Growth in the Canadian biotechnology sector is fostered by fairly sustained industry investment in R&D, financial support from private and public agencies, a supporting regulatory framework, highly skilled human resources, and a general public acceptance of biotech-derived products. Canada's positive relations with the world's most prominent economies and its global reputation for scientific excellence are advantageous in the efforts of Canadian biotechnology companies to expand their businesses to foreign countries. As a result, Canadian biotech exports in all subsectors are expected to continue to grow over the next five years as more products move through the research pipeline and the regulatory process.

The strong position of Canada in biotechnology can be attributed to the combined efforts of government, the universities and private firms. Since the 1980s, the Canadian government has given strong support to the biotechnology sector by investments in laboratory and clinical research, and the infrastructure needed to facilitate the growth of sound scientific and industrial bases. The federal government has developed a Canadian Biotechnology Strategy, which provides a coherent framework for government-supported biotechnology activities. Federal departments and agencies work cooperatively and strategically with provincial governments, academia and private sector partners to integrate a distinctively Canadian approach to biotechnology. Furthermore, both the federal and the provincial governments established policies and are still developing new ones to foster innovation and entrepreneurship in biotechnology.

Almost every link in the Canadian biotechnology value-chain, from academic research through commercialization, is addressed by various public and private sources of finance and by government supported initiatives. Companies and government granting agencies support basic research. A number of newly established venture capital firms deal directly with individual university researchers to finance intellectual property protection and the development of the initial proof of concept. Seed funding for work in the life sciences is now also available from more traditional sources such as the banking community and pools of venture capital.

This section examines the strengths of the Canadian biotechnology innovation system by looking at the salient aspects of the Canadian system of innovation: firstly, it describes the importance of technology clusters (Section 3.1). The section goes on to examine the dynamics of the "triple-helix" (Section 3.2), support for scientific research (Section 3.3), support for commercialization and exports (Section 3.4); and the roles played by incubators (Section 3.5), intellectual property protection (Section 3.6), availability of venture capital (Section 3.7); and finally investigates the competitive cost structure of the Canadian biotechnology industry (Section 3.8).

3.1 Technology clusters

In countries such as Canada with a small and dispersed population and a private sector dominated by small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), clustering is essential to the efficient working of the

innovation system. Technology clusters are geographic entities, usually at the community level, characterized by the growth of a significant concentration of innovative companies around a nucleus of R&D facilities, typically government institutions and/or universities. Involving stakeholders with the government in identifying needs that can be addressed by building on local strengths, and developing solutions and innovation strategies to exploit opportunities, allows teamwork, partnerships and networks to emerge and foster knowledge-based economic growth at the regional level. The Government of Canada, through its innovation strategies developed in cooperation with the industry, its first-class R&D institutes (e.g. the NRC), its Industrial Research Assistance Program (NRC-IRAP) which provide technology advice and support to SMEs, and the Canada Institute for Scientific and Technical Information (NRC-CISTI), plays an essential role in seeding and supporting the growth of technology clusters across Canada.

For example, by establishing the Biotechnology Research Institute (BRI) in Montreal, NRC, together with local universities, has provided an anchor for the establishment of small biotechnology firms. With appropriate technical (NRC, universities) and financial (venture capital) support, some start-ups have eventually achieved a critical mass of expertise, skilled people, capital and entrepreneurial drive, which have been instrumental in attracting new companies and enabling the emergence of yet more spin-offs. The environment rapidly became an innovation “hotspot” in biotechnology, creating local employment and fuelling economic growth in the region. Thus, NRC has been the catalyst for the development of a strong biotechnology cluster in Montreal comprising around 70 private firms, representing some 30% of Canada’s biotech companies.

Overall, NRC has promoted the development of at least 11 technology clusters across Canada in addition to launching a \$110 million five-year Atlantic Initiative to create globally competitive technology clusters that build on Atlantic Canada’s existing strengths. Between 2001 and 2002, NRC received close to \$300 million in additional funds to expand its cluster activities to other communities across Canada. Thus, technology clusters undoubtedly represent an important strength in the Canadian innovation system¹.

3.2 Triple-helix dynamics

The Canadian biotechnology sector is characterized by a dynamic triple-helix structure comprising the state, academia and the private sector. Triple-helix partnerships in biotechnology are common and well established in Canada (Giesecke, 2000). There is a strong tradition of getting actors from these three sectors around the same table with a view to making concerted efforts, developing commonly accepted policies, and undertaking joint projects. In addition, most Canadian biotechnology clusters are located close to leading Canadian universities. Since biotechnology companies are often founded by university researchers, this link with the universities is especially important (Giesecke, 2000).

¹ See NRC Website for more details, http://www.nrc-cnrc.gc.ca/clusters/index_e.html, January 2005

For instance, NRC-PBI is located in Saskatoon, a city that has built a reputation as one of the world's leading centers of agricultural biotechnology. NRC-PBI is located on the campus of the University of Saskatchewan, which also houses Canada's only synchrotron facility and is close to Innovation Place, a research and development park comprising numerous private companies. A powerful synergy between academics, private industry and government research organizations contributes to the strength of this cluster (NRC, 2002).

3.3 Support to the scientific research system

Canada has a high standard of research, a proven track-record, several well-equipped laboratories and a relatively favourable exchange rate all of which serve to attract investments and contracts from other countries, particularly the US. Moreover, Canada has internationally renowned scientists and an increasing numbers of leading-edge biotechnology companies.

The biotechnology sector benefits from a sound research infrastructure supported by several government initiatives, programs, and agencies that promote biotechnology innovation and industry development. A good example is Genome Canada which is a not-for-profit corporation dedicated to developing and implementing a national strategy in genomics research for the benefit of Canadians. It has so far received \$375 million from the Government of Canada in addition to an additional \$60 million which was pledged in the 2004 Federal Budget. Genome Canada has established five Genome Centres across the country (Atlantic, Québec, Ontario, Prairies, and British Columbia) and aims to ensure that Canada becomes a world leader in genomics and proteomics research. The Genome Centres work in close partnership with provincial governments, the private sector and national and international foundations to ensure that Canada becomes a world leader in genomics research in key selected areas such as agriculture, environment, fisheries, forestry and health. These centers are the primary source of funding and information relating to genomics and proteomics in Canada. Genome Canada is committed to partnerships requiring major financial and scientific contributions from other countries including the US, the UK, Japan and China.

The Canadian government has created several programs to support research and innovation. The Canada Foundation for Innovation (CFI) is an independent corporation set up by the Government of Canada to strengthen Canadian research capabilities. Its mandate is to increase the capability of Canadian universities, colleges, hospitals and not-for-profit institutions to carry out scientific research and technology development. The CFI promotes innovation investing in research infrastructures jointly with other institutions. The Canada Research Chairs Program is another ambitious initiative allowing Canadian universities to attract and retain outstanding researchers. Funded by the Government of Canada, the program gives researchers the means to mentor and train top graduate students. Furthermore, the Canadian government has established the Networks of Centres of Excellence (NCE) program, which links academic and industry researchers. Since 1994, five biotechnology NCEs have spun-out more than 33 companies to commercialize new technologies (United-Kingdom Trade & Investment, 2002). Although these initiatives are not specifically targeted

at biotechnology, they certainly play an important role in the strengthening of the science base in this domain.

Other important players supporting the Canadian scientific system include the Canadian Institutes of Health Research (CIHR) and the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada (NSERC). The CIHR is the major federal program responsible for funding health research in Canada. The CIHR uses a multidisciplinary approach through a framework of “virtual” institutes, each dedicated to a specific field that links and supports researchers and helps them in the pursuit of common goals. The institutes support researchers, voluntary health organizations, government and other partners to work together in the shaping of the Canadian research agenda and in transforming research findings into practical applications in Canada’s health system. The CIHR also actively engages in partnerships with provincial governments and not-for-profit organizations, and industry and pharmaceutical companies. NSERC is the primary federal agency investing in university research and training in the natural sciences and engineering. NSERC invests \$850 million in university-based research, supporting more than 10,000 university professors and 20,000 university students². It also encourages more than 500 Canadian companies to invest in university research.

3.4 Commercialization and export support

Canadian biotechnology companies receive support for commercialization from several private and public agencies. The NRC’s Industrial Research Assistance Program (IRAP) offers financial assistance for early stage R&D to help SMEs grow. Increased numbers of collaborations and partnerships have triggered the creation of industry partnership facilities at a number of NRC research institutes.

Another example is the support provided by Trade Team Canada Bio-Industries (TTC BIO), which is a network composed of federal, provincial and regional representatives from industry associations and government agencies. The network aims to foster international business activity within the Canadian bio-industry in the areas of trade, technology transfer and investment. The network’s international business strategy for biotechnology includes promoting Canadian biotech capabilities in the international marketplace, gathering and disseminating foreign market intelligence to Canadian industry, and supporting initiatives that promote a domestic business climate conducive to the growth of an internationally competitive bio-industry in Canada.

Industry Canada’s Technology Partnerships Canada (TPC) is an investment loan fund that was created to provide for the development and export of high-tech products. As of March 31, 2003, TPC’s portfolio includes more than 500 investments totalling \$2.3 billion, which will prop up close to \$10 billion investment from the private sector (Canadian Trade Commissioner Service, 2004). Investment loans must be repaid in full and are intended to help ensure that products with high potential actually reach the market. Sectors within bio-industries supported by the program include

²See NSERC Website for more details, http://www.nserc.gc.ca/about/brief_e.asp, December 2004

therapeutics; diagnostics including clinical trials in phases I and II; agriculture and food; aquaculture; and bio-remediation (Canadian Trade Commissioner Service, 2004).

Biotech companies also receive other forms of assistance to export their products under programs such as EDC, NEXOS and CCC. Export Development Canada (EDC) offers export financing and insurance to Canadian exporters. Additionally, insurance can be provided for larger transactions, that is subject to the terms and conditions established by the buyer. EDC prefers to work through letters of credit, bank credits or bank guarantees. The New Exporters to Overseas program (NEXOS) helps Canadian companies who are hoping to export to Europe. NEXOS trains small companies in the essentials of exporting and provides first-hand knowledge and exposure to European markets. The Canadian Commercial Corporation (CCC) provides finance and favourable repayment conditions to Canadian companies under the Progress Payment Program (PPP), which was developed as a partnership between the major Canadian financial institutions and the CCC with the aim of promoting exports. The CCC acts as prime contractor on behalf of small- and medium-sized enterprises, giving those businesses increased credibility and competitive advantage (Canadian Trade Commissioner Service, 2004).

The federal government created the International Business Opportunities Centre (IBOC), which is a partnership between International Trade Canada and Industry Canada (IC). The Centre matches business opportunities offered by Trade Commissioners abroad with capable Canadian firms, particularly small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Opportunities are handled on a case-by-case basis, spanning all markets and sectors. The Centre uses electronic databases, such as WIN Exports, the Trade Commissioner Service's database of Canadian exporters and their capabilities, and Strategis, Industry Canada's online directory of Canadian companies. The Centre also uses a broad range of contacts in federal and provincial governments and industry associations to identify potential Canadian suppliers of products and services. The Virtual Trade Commissioner (vTC) is an on-line service offered by the Trade Commissioner Service of International Trade Canada. Through a personalized and password-protected Web page, vTC-registered Canadian exporters will receive timely and relevant information on contacts and business opportunities in targeted foreign markets. The vTC offers registered users direct on-line access to market information, including market reports, business news, events and business leads related to industry sectors and markets of interest. Users can request services on line from a trade commissioner responsible for the industry sector in their target markets. They also automatically receive new information as it becomes available.

As is typical in the biotech industry, the most common way to enter the market is through joint-venture and technology-licensing agreements. Other methods of entry include joint research agreements, strategic alliances and partnerships. Of course, each market has a different set of technical and commercial criteria that must be satisfied to commercialize the technology, and it is in a company's interest to obtain the maximum amount of information about the targeted market. Companies with access to privileged information through the intermediaries of market intelligence services have more chance of success. The presence of many independent consultants or firms offering market intelligence services, and the presence of several organizations providing industrial,

commercial and technological advice, provide a competitive advantage for biotech firms and represent an important strength for Canada.

These examples demonstrate that Canadian biotech companies have access to many different initiatives to help in developing their activities and products. In comparison with many other industrialized countries, commercialization and industry support for biotech companies represent an important strength for Canada and certainly contribute to Canada's leading position in biotechnology.

3.5 Incubators

According to the US National Business Incubation Association (NBIA) incubation is a dynamic process of business enterprise development. Incubators nurture young firms, helping them to survive and grow during the start-up period when they are most vulnerable. Incubators provide hands-on management assistance, access to financing and orchestrated exposure to critical business or technical support services. They also offer entrepreneurial firms shared office services, access to equipment, flexible leases and expandable space – all under one roof³.

In fact, the Canadian strategy to develop biotechnology is based, in part, on incubator support. In the early stage of development of the national biotechnology strategy, the Canadian government was already providing funds to institutions such as universities and hospitals to prompt the set up of biotechnology incubators in the medical, plant and animal sectors.

Incubators play an important role in biotechnology start-ups (Industry Canada, 2000) and several Canadian cities have set up this type of facility⁴. Incubators are useful since they promote clustering, an important success factor in most areas. In fact, a Biotechnology Task Force in Ontario claimed that "Incubator companies have a much better chance of success: 80% of companies graduating from such commercialization centres succeed compared to 20% of companies that were not developed through such centres" (Ontario Biotechnology Task Force, 1998). Similarly, in 2000, a Toronto Commissioner for Economic Development wrote a report stating that it "is clear that the presence of incubator facilities in thriving biotech communities such as Boston, Vancouver and Montreal have provided a powerful stimulant to the local economy by nurturing companies from start up to commercial success" (Halstead, 2000).

³ See NBIA Website for more details, http://www.nbia.org/resource_center/what_is/index.php, December 2004

⁴ For example, Halifax has the BioScience Enterprise Centre; Montreal has the *Centre québécois d'innovation en biotechnologie* (CQIB) which was founded in 1996 by the Laval Technopole and the Armand-Frappier Institute; Ottawa has its Biotechnology Incubation Centre (OBIC); the City of Hamilton is building a Health & Biotechnology Incubator in partnership with McMaster University; Winnipeg has an incubator for life science companies located at the University of Manitoba and the NRC's Institute for Biodiagnostics is building a \$15-million incubator; Saskatoon has the Industry Partnership Facility located at NRC's Plant Biotechnology Institute; in Alberta, Calgary Technologies Inc. provides incubator facilities to grow start-up companies, while the Advanced Technology Centre (ATC) provides a business incubator open to qualified entrepreneurs and start-up companies in Edmonton; British Columbia is reaping the rewards of over 71 company spin-offs from University of British Columbia affiliated incubators.

An important player in the incubation of biotechnology enterprises is the NRC. Many of its research institutes provide excellent tools to nurture new, small, technology-based firms. Through co-location, these small enterprises benefit from direct access to NRC facilities and services and from the expertise of its researchers. NRC's capacity to incubate firms has grown considerably in recent years. Specialized incubators often provide firms with access to expensive equipment, which is out of their reach. For example, the NRC Plant Biotechnology Institute's incubator in Saskatoon provides much specialised equipment for example, bioinformatics and robotics equipment, NMR, mass spectrometry, DNA synthesis and DNA sequencing, etc.

Incubators do not merely rent specialized office and laboratory space to biotech start-ups; they help them to obtain capital and make contact with university researchers, patent lawyers and firms that specialize in clinical trials and biotech product marketing and are therefore pivotal to the development of the Canadian biotechnology industry.

3.6 Protection of intellectual property

The area of intellectual property rights has grown in importance as countries recognize that the increasingly important knowledge-based economy is built on ideas rather than on resources or population. For companies to invest, they must be able to capture some of the wealth created by these investments including those made in R&D. If companies have no means of capturing wealth, they will have no incentive to invest and to perform R&D. There are many reasons why companies may not be able to capture wealth, such as the nature of the good produced (public vs. private), market and institutional failures, and information problems. Institutional problems, such as inventions being stolen by competitors, can be resolved through legislation that provides affordable protection for innovators. The flow of intellectual property and of scientific staff necessary for its generation and development means that biotech is highly dependent on universities and research institutes. Top quality research underpins the generation and initial development of viable intellectual property. In many instances aspects of the essential work can be undertaken at other locations where, for example, highly-specific capital equipment is available.

Thus, the property rights issue is an important legislative concern. Although far from being perfect and exempt from criticism, Canada has developed a relatively robust regulatory system for the protection of intellectual property, affording effective protection for companies and researchers that develop new technologies or new products. Firms tend to "vote with their feet" and locate their plants and other infrastructures where they will have the greatest chance to make profits. Canada has adopted a national strategy to align its regulatory systems with those of the US and the European Union, which should allow it to remain competitive and to continue to spur industrial development.

The importance of scientific knowledge as the driving force of progress within the industry means that biotech is very dependent on intellectual property. Key supporting skills and processes include the identification, protection (patenting) and exploitation of intellectual property. One of the strategies used by successful biotech companies is the development of a mixed intellectual property

portfolio. This implies a necessary level of collaboration and co-operation between the state, and the firm or researcher responsible for the new discovery. There must also be a strong commitment to helping researchers to understand the stages and processes involved in intellectual property protection and to facilitating access to the essential legal expertise.

3.7 Venture capital

One of the more important strengths of Canada is its well-developed venture capital (VC) sector. The availability of VC in Canada is a key factor in facilitating the creation and development of biotechnology firms, leading to biotechnology industry expansion. The availability of VC in biotechnology in Canada compares favourably with the situation in the US, taking account of the respective sizes of these countries. For instance, between 1995 and 1999, Canada ranked second among the OECD countries in terms of the percentage of VC to gross domestic product (GDP) and, in 2001 Canada ranked first in terms of availability of VC per GDP (see Figure 16).

Figure 16 Biotechnology venture capital investment per million units of GDP, 1995 and 2001

Source: Devlin (2003)

Thus, Canadian biotechnology firms have good access to VC, even in times of crisis. For example, the VC available to life science firms reached a peak in 2000, but decreased in the following two years. However, VC available to biotechnology firms has remained fairly constant. In contrast, in some countries with an emerging biotechnology industry, for example Ireland, private venture capital firms are reluctant to invest in biotechnology start-ups due to the high level of risk associated with the industry and the long payback time for successful ventures. Irish venture capital funds have thus

had little experience of investing in biotech and development of the biotechnology industry in Ireland has suffered (Bacon, 2003).

3.8 Cost structure

Canada has a competitive business environment. In particular, the tax regime is highly conducive to R&D investment. In fact, the Canadian tax regime creates tremendous opportunities for businesses. By 2005, firms in Canada will have almost a four and a half percentage point tax advantage over US firms. Capital gains taxes have been reduced, with Canada's top rate now being 6.6 percentage points lower than the US equivalent. Canada's capital tax is being reduced in stages over a five year period and will be eliminated by 2008. Finally, R&D enjoys more generous tax treatment in Canada than in the other G7 countries; all current and capital goods expenditures incurred for R&D can be deducted to reduce tax liability in the current year or can be carried over to future years (Rock, 2003).

Partly because of these considerable fiscal advantages, Canada has become the destination of choice for firms seeking to establish new operations. This was clearly demonstrated in a 2002 study conducted by KPMG, which compared the basic costs of doing business across the G7 countries (plus Austria and the Netherlands). Canada emerged as the single most competitive country in terms of business costs. The KPMG study concluded that Canada enjoys a substantial and constant cost advantage over the US in all industries and more particularly so in those requiring a high proportion of skilled workers (KPMG, 1999). Another study conducted by KPMG Consulting found that Canada offers the greatest cost advantage in biomedical and biotechnology R&D with lower labour costs than the UK, which ranked second and the US, which ranked eighth (UK Trade & Investment, 2002).

4 Discussion and conclusion

The development of the biotechnology industry in the 1980s and 1990s has been conducive to significant scientific progress in diverse fields and has had an important impact on the Canadian economy. The academic, private and government sectors, the so-called triple-helix dynamic, have helped Canada become a world leader in biotechnology. This dynamic innovation system provides companies, the heart of the biotechnology industry, with access to well equipped facilities, services and knowledge that are often vital to their success. The creation of incubators, an important strength of Canada, was catalyzed by the Canadian biotechnology strategy. These infrastructures together with Canadian policies and initiatives for commercialization are among the key factors contributing to the development of the Canadian biotechnology industry.

The advantages conferred by Canadian infrastructures are enhanced by a well-developed venture capital industry and by considerable fiscal advantages and low-cost production. In addition, biotech companies have access to an important network of experts who can provide market intelligence, marketing advice, and production services that are all recognized as playing a critical role in company success. These highly competitive advantages work to attract new companies to Canada. Canadian companies and research organisations are able to attract international business partners as the country is also well positioned to act as a gateway to the North American market. Small and medium-sized Canadian companies offering a mix of innovation, low-cost production, and excellent research capability with a skilled labour force make ideal allies for international partners.

Overall, Canada has a fairly good position in biotechnology science ranking 6th, on a par with France, for the period spanning 1992 to 2003. In terms of patenting of biotech inventions, Canada performance is even better: it is ranked 2nd behind the US, and on a par with Denmark. This indicates the strength of the Canadian biotechnology industry since the commercial interests of companies often push them to protect, rather than to publish their findings in the public domain.

The most active institutions in biotechnology in Canada are the universities with the University of Toronto ranked 1st, McGill University 2nd and the University of British Columbia 3rd. Among the hospitals, the leading institutions are Mount Sinai Hospital of Toronto, the Hospital for Sick Children and the University Health Network. The leading companies are Merck & Co., Aventis and Aquabounty Farms for scientific output, and Aventis, Visible Genetics and Allelix Biopharmaceuticals for technological output.

Most research activities and companies in the biotechnology sector are directed towards health-related applications as can be seen from the results of the current study. About 50% of the research output in biotechnology in Canada is related to biomedical research and 30% to clinical medicine. In terms of protection of intellectual property, 44% of technology falls in the human health sector. The predominance of the health sector in biotechnology is also apparent from identified niche strengths of which about 70% are related to human health. These include the study of diabetes, musculoskeletal disorders, hormones, stem cells, drug resistance mechanisms, cardiovascular diseases, psychological and neurological disorders, and cancer. Importantly though, given its competitive advantages, the most "natural" strengths of Canada in biotechnology relate to natural resources and include forestry, aquatic sciences, environmental sciences and animal sciences.

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